
IMPACT OF BUDGET IMPLEMENTATION ON 2023 FISCAL PERFORMANCE RANKINGS BY STATES IN NIGERIA.

Goodman Daniel Diegha, PhD

Dept of Economics, University of Africa Toru-Orua,
Bayelsa State, Nigeria. +2348035481251

Okowa I. Okowa

General Studies KenPoly Bori, Rivers State, Nigeria

Abstract;

The study examined impact of revenue implementation of 2023 fiscal performance ranking by thirty five states in Nigeria in the six geopolitical zones in the country. The paper made use of the recorded amount of received revenue in 2023 fiscal year sources from CBN and Nigerian statistical Bulletin to determine the ranking of states based on their fiscal performance, allocation received and effect of the environment on the provision of fiscal infrastructure. The paper anchored on “Overhang Debt Theory” the paper adopted descriptive statistics of frequency table, percentages and bar charts to answer the objective question and adopted T-test statistics to test the hypotheses. Findings revealed that Benue state got the highest allocation for North-West geopolitical zone Imo state got the highest allocation for South-East geopolitical zone. For the South-South geopolitical zone, Bayelsa state got the highest allocation for South-South geopolitical zone and Ekiti state got the highest for South-East geopolitical zone. It was found that there was no significant relationship between amount received and fiscal performance in the Bayelsa state. There was significant relationship between revenue received and infrastructural performance in Rivers state, Nigeria. By Geopolitical zones, South-West and North-West got the highest allocation for the 2023 fiscal year. The study recommended that the State governors should be properly checkmated by the states assemblies to ensure judicious utilization of fund received. Federal government Financial Crimes Commission should sit up in prosecuting fraudulent leaders who failed to adequately make use of public funds and both state and national assemblies must stand against budget padding which is the root of corruption in agencies in the country.

Keywords: Impact, Budget Implementation, Fiscal Performance, Nigeria

Introduction

In every country, infrastructural development of states is dependent of the amount budgeted to capital expenditure in the budget. One of the major benefits is that every sector of the economy is given attention and included in the economic recovery growth plan (ERGP) and its deliverables specifically evaluated. In budgetary allocation, whatever that constitutes expenditure and income are spelt out and cost of funding expenditures allocated to every sector of the economy. Some experts might say that the country might not be borrowing too fast as debt-to-GDP is still approximately 29% at the end of 2019, but the complete story is that Nigeria has failed to gather revenues and its leaders do not want to take drastic measures required to significantly rationalize expenditure. While variables are involved in a holistic analysis approach, this paper conducts a disaggregated analysis of funding of the three armed forces of Nigeria within eight year period. It also considers the sector's contribution to economic growth as it affects the entire country (Felix, 2013). According to the Budget Office, the federal government's actual deficits in the last five years have stood at N1.52tn for 2015, N2.19tn in 2016, N3.80tn in 2017, N3.64tn in 2018 and N4.17tn in 2019. Managing the budget effectively for the provision of infrastructure is the essence is to effectively manage and harness resources, and to ensure accountability, probity equity and fairness. The consequence of this has been the rising cost of debt servicing which grew from N624bn in 2014 to N2.45tn in 2019. Nigeria has continued to trample on fiscal sustainability as debt service to revenue ratio has grown to 94%. This is a gross anomaly in the public finance analysis of a sustainable entity. Security of a nation in air, land and sea is the responsibility of the three armed forces of the country. It is necessary to get them equipped all the time with all the ammunitions for combat readiness.

According to UNESCO recommendation, Budgetary allocations are required more to be channeled to the armed forces, followed by education with 15 to 20 per cents of the total budget. Records show that from the 1960s, armed forces budgetary allocations were recorded high and have helped in growing the economy through peace and stability which enabled businesses to flourish in the country (Olayide & Ikpi, 2010). However, in the past decade, it has been observed that budgetary allocations to the armed forces have continued to dwindle. This was in the face of security confrontation with Boko Haram terrorists and insurgency across the length and breadth of the country. In split of the huge budgetary allocations to the armed forces (army, Navy and Air force) in the last four (4) years fighting insurgency and purchase of military hardwares have not been encouraging as the story have been that the terrorists are with better and more sophisticated weapons than the country's military. The explanation is that operational capabilities of the army have reduced greatly to the extent that they run away from the terrorists when attached. Military aircrafts are sometimes not functional to smoke the terrorist out of the forest and hide outs. The question raised is whether the state governors in Nigeria performed creditably in their various states terms provision of fiscal infrastructure given the amount budgeted for the 2022 fiscal year. To find out the reality about expenditure on infrastructure, it became necessary to conduct investigation on the provision of fiscal infrastructure in 2022 in various states of the federation. This paper is contributes to the pool of literature in this topic. It is important as it brings to reality issues concerning budgetary allocations to the armed forces. It explains the extent of judicious utilization of amount contained in the capital expenditure in the 2022 fiscal year budget.

Problem Statement

Performances of states in the six geopolitical zones of the country have become a concern to the citizens. This is as a result of the huge amounts received as allocations in 2023. This

could also be attributed to the increasing price of crude in the international market. It is the responsibility of the state government to provide not only basic infrastructure to the people such as good roads, electricity, hospitals, security of life and property and others. It is to the bewilderment of the general public that the citizens are suffering due to lack of these fiscal infrastructures. Besides, every year, huge sums are budgeted for infrastructural developments which do not reflect in the environment to show that such budgets are being spent. These states have been ranked according to their individual performances in the year 2023 following the funds received for the fiscal year. The question raised is, how well has the funds received reflected in the provision of fiscal infrastructures in the states. To provide answer to this question this study attempts to investigate impact of budget implementation on 2023 fiscal performance rankings by states in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The paper investigated impact of budget implementation on 2022 fiscal performance in Nigerian. Specific objectives of the paper were to;

- (i) identify the ranking of states fiscal performance of states
- (ii) examine the effect of revenue allocations on fiscal performance of states
- (iii) effect of environment on fiscal performance of states

Research Question

Answer to the following questions provides guide to objectives of the study;

- (a) to what extent is the ranking of fiscal performance in the states?
- (b) to what extent is the effect of revenue allocations on fiscal performance in the states?
- (c) what is the extent of and environmental fiscal performance in the states?

Study Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested to ascertain the impact of states budgets on fiscal performance.

1. there is no significant relationship between positive political environment and fiscal Performance in the states.
2. there is no significant relationship between budget amount and fiscal performance of states

This study goes a long way in bringing to reality the extent of expenditures of the states executives in providing fiscal infrastructure in their respective states in Nigeria. The pool of literature will be boosted by the addition of this work. The paper is a stepping stone to further studies in this direction. It would further explain the need for accountability in terms of public expenditure by the state executives.

Conceptual Clarification

Budget Implementation; Budgets explains the process of envisaging the expenditure and income outlay of an institution or government with a view to spending based on the outlays. The process of spending based on the actual budget is the implementation. Budget could be deficit or surplus. Deficit budgeting is usually serviced through borrowing. This occurs where this is appropriation and it could be financed through borrowing.

Fiscal Performance; Fiscal performance in an economy is explained in term of development of infrastructure. Fiscal policy is the use of government spending and taxation to influence the economy. Governments typically use fiscal policy to promote strong and sustainable

growth and reduce poverty. Performance is limited by paucity of revenue and enabling business environment and other major variables.

Ranking; This explains categorization of an entity, determine performance or grade and position. Ranking could mean placement for assessment of how well an activity could be accepted for decision making.

Literature Review

2023 Fiscal Performance by Nigerian States

In the study, states are ranked A, B and C based on their performance. States that rank higher on Index A have comparatively limited dependence on federally distributed revenue for their operations and thus have greater viability if they were to theoretically exist as an independent entity. In contrast, states that rank lower on Index A either need to work harder on growing their Internally Generated Revenue considering the size of their operating expenses or work on pruning their operating expenses. The lower ranking states also have more work to do to improve their business enabling environment and enhance their domestic resource mobilization capacity.

There are indices for accessing the fiscal performance of states. These indices are; limited dependence on revenue distributed by federal government, growth in internally generated revenue, more reserve public revenue after fulfilling repayment obligations to lenders, more ability to borrow more due to their comparatively sustainable debt profiles, and states with priority to investing in capital expenditure compared to their operating expenses.

Rivers Maintains Top Overall Fiscal Performance Position among Nigeria's 36 states – Report

“Index A examines states’ ability to meet Operating Expenses (Recurrent Expenditure) with only their Internally Generated Revenue; Index A1 looks at the percentage year-on-year growth of each state’s Internally Generated Revenue. “Index B reviews states’ ability to cover all operating expenses and loan repayment obligations with their Total Revenue (Internally Generated Revenue + Statutory Transfers + Aids and Grants) without resorting to borrowing. “Index C estimates the debt sustainability of the states using four major Indicators: A. Debt as a per cent of GDP, B. Debt as a per cent of Revenue, C. Debt service as a per cent of Revenue and D. Personnel Cost as a per cent of Revenue. “Index D evaluates the degree to which each State is prioritizing capital expenditure concerning their operating expenses (recurrent expenditure),” he explained. According to him, two states, Kaduna and Cross River, made it to the top five on the overall fiscal performance ranking; Yobe dropped to the bottom five having fallen 13 places from 21st in 2021 to 34th position in 2022.

Comparatively, the operating expenses of Yobe and Bayelsa (the least ranked states on index A) were more than seven times the revenues generated by both states internally, reinforcing the heavy reliance on federal transfers and budget support to fund their budgets. On index A1, save for three states, which ranked the least – Anambra, Kogi and Kebbi – 33 states experienced an increase in their IGR from the previous year, with 13 states growing their IGR by more than 50 per cent. The four states with the highest dollar-denominated debt (250 million dollars and above) – Lagos, Kaduna, Cross River and Edo – are the most susceptible to exchange rate volatility,” he explained that cumulative expenditure of the 36 states increased by 27 per cent from N5.23 trillion in 2020 to N6.64 trillion in 2021. Notwithstanding, while 31 states increased their total expenditure from the previous year, five states reduced their expenditure with Zamfara having the highest decline of 15.59 per cent.

Overhang Debt Theory

However, this paper is predicated on an Overhang Debt Theory formulated to support public debt burden. According to Overhang Debt Kruman, (198), overhang Debt Theory explains the possibility of larger government debt than the repayment ability of the country will be face discouragement due to expect cost of servicing the debt. This discouragement will affect the possibility of further incurring foreign and domestic investments. Future investors will be discouraged due to the understanding that they may experience more taxes as they produce to enable the government service her hanging public debts. Therefore, more productions will attract more taxation hence, their less willingness to incur costs of investment just to increase output in the future (Gordn & Cosimo, 2018). Public debt accumulation is considered as future output tax and savings and investment reduction incentive. Debt service requirement reduces available fund for investment and it is a liquidity binding constraint on debt with possibility of restraining investment thereby retarding economic growth and development

(Coccia, 2017). It is the suggestion of the theory that effect on the growth through capital accumulation or growth of productivity may occur. The bottom-line is that the huge fund used in servicing huge public debt drains resources that would have been made available for investment in most critical sectors of the economy. For developing nations, huge debt servicing reduces resources and dims possible growth. Increased debt burden propels capital flight and creates devaluation risk, taxation and the zeal to protect real financial assets value while capital flight depletes domestic savings investment thereby reducing economic growth, debt serving capacity and tax base

Empirical Review

Literature is crowded with studies on performing states in Nigeria visa-vise federal allocation and revenue through derivation formula especially as it concerns Niger Delta region in the South-South geopolitical zone: Ayeni & Afolabi, (2015): Edame, & Okoi, (2015): Audu, (2012). Onyema and Onuoha (2019) investigated fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria the study focus was on economic growth. Multiple regressions were adopted for the analysis. It was discovered that fiscal policy promoted economic growth over the years. It was further found that the proxied variables: government expenditure, social services and taxes were measures to positively influence the economic development while government expenditure negatively related to economic development. M Analysis of budget and economic development was empirically analyzed by Udoh, Chegwe, Nyema and Ndaburoma, (2023). The study focused on budgeting and its implementation. The paper adopted multiple regressions and correlation analysis was adopted for data analysis. It was found that there was a low positive statistically significant effect on public capital expenditure on both life expectancy index but a low significant effect on recurrent expenditure on per capita income and life expectancy index.

Enyoghasim, Ogwuru, Agbanike, Anochiwa and Agu, (2021) conducted a study on macroeconomic performance of fiscal policy in Nigeria. Focus of the study was on the growth of the gross domestic product. The study adopted Econometric Techniques of Ordinary Least Squares and Co-integration/error correction for the data analysis. It was revealed that there are serious implications of fiscal policy on economic growth evidences by the coefficient of determination of the model.

Impact of fiscal policy on Nigeria economy was studied by Audu, (2012). Focus of the study was on the causal relationship between supply of money, export, fiscal deficit. The study employed the Co-integration Error Correction Mechanism (ECM), a two band recursive least

square of Co-integration and Error Correction to test the economic stability. It was found that causal significant relationship existed between the research variables and gross domestic product. Fiscal policies and domestic product showed causal relationship with exports. A Chow approach in understanding fiscal deficits and Economic Growth in Nigeria was investigated by Edame and Okoi, (2015). Focus of the study was on democratic regimes poor performance. The study adopted Chow endogenous break test, unit root and co-integration tests for the study analysis. The study discovered that there was significant economic growth impact during the military regimes based on fiscal deficit. However, the fiscal deficit had no impact on economic growth during the democratic regimes. In the same vein, there was no significant impact of the interest rate during the military regime while it had significant impact on economic growth during the democratic era.

Tax revenue, infrastructural development and economic growth in Nigeria was examined by Ayeni and Afolabi, (2015). The study focused on effect of collected tax revenue. Both Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test and Phillip Perron (PP) test, were adopted while the Johansen Co-integration test was also utilized. It was found that there was unidirectional causality from tax revenue to economic growth and from economic growth to fiscal infrastructure. There was also a bi-directional causality between tax revenue and infrastructural development. Again, tax revenue influenced economic growth and infrastructural development but failed to impact significantly positive on the growth of the economy.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted descriptive statistics of frequency tables, percentages, bar charts to attain to the objective questions. It utilized the publication of Budget (2023) and Debt Management Office (DMO) in evaluating facts about Debt burden as criterion for determining the fiscal infrastructure investment of the 36 states of the federation for 2023. This analysis is conducted based on the following established indices; (a) Ranking based on federal allocation or revenue (b) budget fiscal performance, (b) ranking of states fiscal performance (c) political and environmental fiscal performances

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics of tables, frequencies, percentages and bar charts were adopted for this study data analysis.

Data Presentation

Table 1. Federal revenue to states and their Fiscal Performance Ranking 2023

S/N	States	Amount Received (₦)	Fiscal Performance Ranking
1	Delta State	18,271,814,326.61	12
2	AkwaIbom	14,060,495,671.30	24
3	Rivers	12,238,261,885.29	1
4	Bayelsa	10,392,154,207.93	35
5	Lagos	9,337,714,307.47	3
6	Kano	6,349,060,000.57	7
7	Kaduna	110,209,555.96	2
8	Katsina	3,249,378,997.03	21
9	Kwara	4,857,452,744.75	8
10	Borno	4,713,494,910.19	20
11	Jigawa	4,517,584,630.14	23
12	Oyo	4,450,789,359.46	11
13	Ondo	4,412,463,776.95	19
14	Imo	4,332,718,771.10	26
15	Niger	4,295,524,964.84	31
16	Anambra	4,145,654,356.19	6
17	Sokoto	4,255,906,404.68	14
18	Benue	4,128,248,900.82	36
19	Kebbi	4,075,814,093.10	15
20	Yobe	3,980,459,295.49	34
21	Enugu	3,968,244,429.89	16
22	Kogi	3,940,071,065.02	27
23	Bauchi	3,893,684,440.36	22
24	Adamawa	3,699,672,900.11	33
25	Taraba	3,561,846,067.21	32
26	Enonyi	3,512,337,248.19	5
27	Nasarawa	3,417,877,769.57	13
28	Plateau	3,387,447,622.55	29
29	Zamfara	3,139,845,465.47	25
30	Abia	4,095,616,677.18	18
31	Ekiti	3,121,178,193.00	30
32	Gombe	3,104,688,765.80	28
33	Cross River	2,880,631,536.23	4
34	Osun	2,721,652,592.48	17
35	Edo	2,354,685,783.46	9

Source: wwyoubudgit.com

Analysis of Data

To attain to the study objectives, the study tried to answer the questions;

- (a) Extent is the ranking of fiscal performance in the states

Fig. 1 North-Central Geopolitical Zone

Fig. 2 North East Geopolitical Zone

Figure 1 revealed fiscal performance by ranking in North-Central geopolitical zones. It showed that highest state with fiscal performance ranking was Benue state with 36 percents followed by Niger state with 31 percents. Third in the ranking is Plateau state with 29 percents while Kogi state had 27 percents. The least on the ranking were Nasarawa and Kwara states with 13 and 8 percents respectively.

For North-East geopolitical zone as shown in figure 2, fiscal ranking revealed that the highest in the ranking was Yobe state with 34 percents followed by Adamawa state with 33 percents. third in the ranking is Taraba state with 32 percents while fourth position is Gombe state with 28 percents. The least states were Bauchi and Borno states with 22 and 20 percents respectively.

Fig 3 North-West Geopolitical Zone

Fig 4 South-East Geopolitical Zone

Figure 3 revealed fiscal performance ranking for states in North-West geopolitical zone. The ranking reviewed that the highest in the ranking for the geopolitical zone is Zamfara state with 25 percents while this is followed by Jigawa state with 23 percents. Third in the ranking is Katsina state with 21 percents. This is followed by Kebbi state with 15 percents with fourth rank reflected in Sokoto states with 14 percents. The least states in the fiscal performance ranking were Kano and Kaduna with 7 and 2 percents respectively.

For South-East geopolitical zone as shown in figure 4 revealed that the highest ranking went to Imo states with 26 percents while the second ranking went to Abia state with 18 percents. third in the ranking went to Enugu state with 16 percents. least in the ranking were Anambra and Ebonyi states with 6 and 5 percents respectively.

Fig 5 South-South Geopolitical Zone (Niger Delta). Fig. 6 South-East Geopolitical Zone

Figure 5 for South-South geopolitical zone revealed that the highest state in the fiscal performance ranking was Bayelsa state with 35 percents while she is followed by Akwa Ibom state with 24 percents. The third position went to Delta states with 12 percents. The third position in the ranking went to Edo state with 9 percents. The least fiscal performance ranked states were Cross River and Rivers with 4 and 1 percent respectively.

For South-East geopolitical zone as shown in figure 6, revealed that Ekiti states had the highest fiscal performance ranking with 30 percents. The second positing went to Ondo state with 19 per cents. The third position was clinched by Osun state with 17 percents. the third position went to Oyo state with 11 percents. The least in the ranking were Ogun and Lagos states with 10 and 3 percents respectively.

(b) Extent of effect of revenue allocations on fiscal performance in the states of the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria.

Table 2.

S/N	Geopolitical Zones	States	Amount Received (₦)	S/N	Geopolitical Zones	State	Amount Received (₦)
1.	North – Central (Middle Belt)	Benue.	4,128,248,900.82	4.	North – West	Jigawa	4,517,584,630.14
		Kogi	3,940,071,065.02			Kaduna	110,209,555.96
		Kwara	4,857,452,744.75			Kano	6,349,060,000.57
		Nassarawa	3,417,877,769.57			Katsina	3,249,378,997.03
		Niger	4,295,524,964.84			Kebbi	4,075,814,093.10
		Plateau	3,387,447,622.55			Sokoto	4,255,906,404.68
		Abuja				Zamfara	3,139,845,465.47
2.	North – East	Adamawa	3,699,672,900.11	5.	South – West	Ekiti .	3,121,178,193.00
		Bauchi	3,893,684,440.36			Lagos	9,337,714,307.47
		Borno	4,713,494,910.19			Ogun	4,392,632,406.57
		Gombe	3,104,688,765.80			Ondo	4,412,463,776.95
		Taraba	3,561,846,067.21			Osun	2,721,652,592.48
		Yobe	3,980,459,295.49			Oyo	4,450,789,359.46
3.	South – South	Akwa/Ibom.	14,060,495,671.30	6.	South – East	Abia	4,095,616,677.18
		Bayelsa	10,392,154,207.93			Anambra	4,145,654,356.19
		Cross River	2,880,631,536.23			Ebonyi	3,512,337,248.19
		Rivers	12,238,261,885.29			Enugu	3,968,244,429.89

	(Niger Delta)	Edo	5,687,908,354.48			Imo	4,332,718,771.10
		Delta	18,271,814,326.61				

From table 2, the performance of states was being attributed to debt serving from their internally generated and received monthly allocations. Another aspect was dwindling allocations. Under North-Central geopolitical zone (Middle Belt), Benue state received revenue allocation of ₦4, 128,248,900.82. A total sum of 3940071065.02 was received by Kogi state while Kwara and Nasarawa states received ₦4, 857,452,744.75 and ₦3, 417,877,769.57 respectively, while Niger and Plateau states got a total sum of ₦4,295,524,964.84 and ₦3,387,447,622.55 respectively totaling N240,266,230.68

For North-East geopolitical zone, Adamawa and Bauchi State secured the sum of ₦3, 699,672,900.11 and ₦3, 893,684,440.36 as allocation respectively. Borno and Gombe states got the sum of ₦4,713,494,910.19 and ₦3,104,688,765.80 respectively while Taraba and Yobe states received allocations totally ₦3,561,846,067.21 and ₦3,980,459,295.49 each with the period reviewed. All totaling N229, 538,463.79

For the South-South (Niger Delta region), the formally 6 states not 9 states of the oil producing states receives a total sum of six hundred and thirty-five billion, three hundred and twelve Million, six hundred and fifty nine hundred and eighty two kobo (N635,312,659.82). On a disaggregated level, Delta got the highest amount totally eighteen billion, two-hundred and seventy one million, eight hundred and fourteen million, three hundred and twenty-six naira, sixty-one kobo (₦18, 271,814,326.61) followed by Akwa/Ibom with a total sum of ₦14, 060,495,671.30 respectively. Third on the list is Rivers state with the sum of ₦12, 238,261,885.29 while Bayelsa and Edo states received ₦10, 392,154,207.93 and ₦5, 687,908,354.48 respectively. Least in the allocations receipt for the period reviewed was Cross Rivers with the sum of N2, 880,631,536.23.

For the North-West, a cumulative total of three trillion, one hundred and thirty nine billion, eight hundred and forty-five million, four hundred and sixty five thousand forty seven kobo (₦18, 271,814,326.61) was received as allocations during the period. At an aggregated level, Jigawa state received the sum of ₦4, 517,584,630.14 for the fiscal year 2023 while Kaduna state got an allocation totaling ₦110, 209,555.96. Other states like Kano and Katsina received a total sum of ₦6, 349,060,000.57 and ₦3, 249,378,997.03 respectively. States like Kebbi and Sokoto got ₦4,075,814,093.10 and ₦4,255,906,404.68 while the least was Zamfara which received ₦3,139,845,465.47 only for the fiscal year.

For South-West, cumulatively, a total sum of three hundred and seventy-seven billion, seven hundred and forty one million, four hundred and forty nine naira forty-three kobo was received (₦377,741,449.43). Individually, Lagos state got the sum of ₦9, 337,714,307.47 to top the ranking for the geopolitical zone. Ekiti state and Ogun state received the sum of ₦3,121,178,193.00 and ₦4,392,632,406.57 respectively for the fiscal year while Ondo and Osun received the sum of ₦4,412,463,776.95 and ₦2,721,652,592.48 each. And the sum of ₦4, 450,789,359.46 was received by Oyo state for the fiscal year reviewed.

For the South-East, a cumulative sum of two hundred billion, five-hundred and forty-five million, seven and forty five thousand naira eighty three kobo (₦200, 545,714.83) was received by South-East geopolitical zone for the fiscal year 2023. On a disaggregated level, Imo state topped the rank with the sum of N4, 332,718,771.10. This was followed by Anambra state with the sum of ₦4,145,654,356.19 while Abia got a total sum of ₦4,095,616,677.18.

Ebonyi and Enugu received the sum of ₦3, 512,337,248.19 and ₦3, 968,244,429.89 respectively for the fiscal year.

(c) the extent of and environmental fiscal performance in the states

The environment is a major motivator of investment in a developing country like Nigeria. It explains facilities not limited to; systems services and improvement projects related to: water, waste and recycling, climate adaptation and resilience, agriculture, land conservation parks and recreation and environmental markets. These public facilities are not adequate in the states to enable both political and environmental development.

The states are lacking in the provision of these public facilities that will to a large extent motivate improvement in the development of science and technology. It is essential condition for economic development and wealth creation via inter-sectoral linkages such as provision of raw materials for manufacturing such as resources for production of goods and services. Provision of foreign exchange earnings through export market. The natural resources can be exported to earn revenue for the states. Increase in export of resources. The environmental pollutions arising from bunkering activities has reduced the volume of crude exports on daily basis.

Insecurity has given rise to kidnappings in various parts of the country. This has reduced the farming activities as men and women can no longer go the farms to cultivate (). The hazardous activities from pipeline leakages has increased the health hazards in the regions with attendant cases of cancer, cerebral meningitis, skin diseases and deaths especially in the oil producing part of the country.

Test of Hypotheses

The study hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics in the following procedure;

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{S_1^2}{n_1 - 1} + \frac{S_2^2}{n_2 - 1}}}$$

Hypothesis 1

1. there is no significant relationship between positive political environment and fiscal Performance in the states.

Table 3. Relationship between fiscal infrastructural provision and total revenue received for 2023 fiscal year in South-South Geopolitical zone (using Rivers and Bayelsa states)

Zone	South-South Geopolitical zone	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision at p >.05
Hospitals	Rivers State	12,238,261,885.29	12.93	1.51	1.062	2.166	1.960	P=1.022
	Bayelsa State							p=0.436
Rd. construction		10,392,154,207.93	12.98	1.47	1.008	0.782	1.960	NS, p>.05

Decision rule: if $p < .05$ reject H_0 , else retain H_0 . S= Significant, $p < .05$ NS= Not Significant $p > .05$

Source: Computed from field data, 2023.

Analysis in table 4 revealed that for South-South geopolitical zone, Rivers State, which is a Niger Delta State, was used among the states in South-South, result showed there is positive significant relationship between total amount received as allocation and the fiscal infrastructural provision in the state. In all, there is no difference in revenue allocation and developmental strides found the state for 2023 fiscal year ($t_{1.51, 1.022} = -1.062, p > .05$) while there is no significant relationship between received allocation and fiscal infrastructural provision in Bayelsa state ($t_{1.47, 0.025} = 0.782, p > .05$). This may be associated with the difference in amount received ₦12, 238,261,885.29 - ₦10, 392,154,207.93 coupled with the state's indebtedness to banks.

Hypothesis 2

1. there is no significant relationship between budget amount and fiscal performance of states

Research Question 2. There is not significant relationship between environmental pollution and health hazard of residents of Niger Delta region.

Table 5. Relationship between fiscal infrastructural provision and revenue received (Kwara and Plateau states)

Zone	North-Central geopolitical zone	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision at $p > .05$
Pipe Borne Water	Kwara state	4,857,452,744.75	4.08	1.97	1.203	-4.385	1.960	P=0.009 S. $p > 1.45$
Provision of Schools	Plateau state	3,387,447,622.55	3.80	1.95	0.78	-1.087	1.960	p=0.280 NS, $p > .05$

Decision rule: from our probability value, if $p < .05$ reject H_0 , else retain H_0 ; S= Significant, $p < .05$
 NS= Not Significant $p > .05$).

Source: Computed from field data, 2011.

Table 5 analysis for the North-central geopolitical zone (Middle-belt), using Kwara and Plateau states. It was discovered that there is a significant relationship between fiscal performance in Kwara state and Plateau state ($t_{1.203, 1.45} = -4.385, p < .05$), with a difference in amount reviewed ₦4,857,452,744.75 - ₦3,387,447,622.55 with the 2023 fiscal year reviewed. It may also be as a result of the state's debt burden.

Table 6. Summary of allocations Received by geopolitical zones

S/N	Geopolitical Zone	Total Amount Received (₦)
1.	North-Central (Middle-Belt)	240,266,230.68
2.	North-East	229, 538,463.79
3.	South-South	635,312,659.82
4.	North-West	3, 139,845,465.47
5.	South-west	18, 271,814,326.61
6.	South-East	200, 545,714.83

As shown in table 6, ranking by geopolitical zone, revealed that cumulatively, South-South geopolitical zone received the highest allocation (₦18, 271,814,326.61) for fiscal 2023 year. It was followed by North-West Geopolitical zones with ₦3, 139,845,465.47 allocations for the period reviewed. Third and fourth ranking on the list were South-South and North-Central geopolitical zones with ₦635, 312,659.82 and ₦240, 266,230.68 revenue allocations respectively for the fiscal year while North-East and South-South were least on the ranking

by geopolitical zones with ₦229, 538,463.79 and ₦200, 545,714.83 respectively for the 2023 reviewed fiscal year.

Conclusion

The implementation of budgetary allocations for the 2023 fiscal year in all the states of the federation was investigated and the study came up with the following results; it was revealed that Benue state got the highest allocation for North-West geopolitical zone Imo state got the highest allocation for South-East geopolitical zone. For the South-South geopolitical zone, Bayelsa state got the highest allocation for South-South geopolitical zone and Ekiti state got the highest for South-East geopolitical zone. It was found that there was no significant relationship between amount received and fiscal performance in the Bayelsa state. There was significant relationship between revenue received and infrastructural performance in Rivers state, Nigeria. By Geopolitical zones, South-West and North-West got the highest allocation for the 2023 fiscal year.

Recommendations

Following the revealed results and if the states and country are to experience fiscal infrastructure, the following recommendations should be adopted by the government.

1. State governors should be properly checkmated by the states assemblies to ensure judicious utilization of fund received.
2. Federal government Financial Crimes Commission should sit up in prosecuting fraudulent leaders who failed to adequately make use of public funds.
3. Both state and national assemblies must stand against budget padding which is the root of corruption in agencies in the country.

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